

Comparative effect of *Metarhizium anisopliae*– Meta31 as Biocontrol agent on African Rice Gall Midge (*Orseolia oryzivora*) Eggs infestation on Rice Plant

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ABSTRACT

Background: African Rice Gall Midge (AfRGM) *Orseolia oryzivora* Harris & Gagné (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), is a major insect pest primarily of rainfed and irrigated lowland rice in Africa. Heavy yield losses of 25–100% have been recorded in farmers' fields thereby reducing the production capacity to very low ebb in an endemic situation. It is therefore necessary to provide quality measures that are germane to managing the menace of this pest on rice to enhance food security.

Objectives: Two entomopathogenic fungi with three strains each were evaluated in this study to assess their efficacy on rice seedlings infested with eggs of AfRGM.

Methods: Three strains each of the two fungi was tested on rice seedling infested with AfRGM eggs in the screen cage placed under screen house. Infestation, physiological and agronomical data were taken and evaluated.

Results: The study showed that *M. anisopliae* Meta31 had the greatest control effect on AfRGM eggs with 84.13±0.9% non-infested tillers. The percentage of non-infested tiller advantage over the control followed the same trend with *M. anisopliae* Meta31 having the greatest value of 22.19±0.25%. Tiller infestation was negatively correlated with chlorophyll content, leaf breadth and grain number.

Conclusion: The tiller infestation showed the efficacy of *M. anisopliae* Meta31 and it can be used as biocontrol agent for controlling the infestation of AfRGM without any negative effect on the plant health.

Keywords: *Metarhizium anisopliae*, entomopathogenic, fungi, AfRGM eggs, infestation, biocontrol

INTRODUCTION

African Rice Gall Midge (AfRGM) *Orseolia oryzivora* Harris & Gagné (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), is a major insect pest primarily of rainfed and irrigated lowland rice in Africa. Heavy yield losses of 25–100% have been recorded in farmers' fields thereby reducing the production capacity to very low ebb in an endemic situation (Ogah and Nwilene, 2014). It is therefore necessary to provide quality measures that are germane to managing the menace of this pest on rice to enhance food security.

Different methods have been developed to prevent the menace of insect infestation in the field. Some methods are limited in one form or the other. The AfRGM pest undergoes complete metamorphosis. The second instar-larva is the most destructive stage of this pest. If the pest cycle is obstructed during the egg phase, the cycle will break and the

insect will not reach the destructive stage, thereby the infestation is controlled. The high yielding genetics are not left behind in the pest infestation and so they cannot be used because they are susceptible to major biotic constraints (pests and diseases) (Nwilene *et al.*, 2011). Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) are considered as a rich source of bioactive compounds for controlling pests (Kaaya and Hassan, 2000; Ginsberg *et al.* 2002). When spores of EPF come in contact with the cuticle of a susceptible insect, chitinase are secreted to penetrate the cuticle, allowing the fungus to proliferate throughout the insect's body (Smith *et al.*, 1981). The EPF produce toxins that reduces insect feeding and eventually kill the host insect (Scholte *et al.*, 2005; Scholte *et al.*, 2006). Specifically, the entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana*

produce the toxins Destruxin B and Beauvericin respectively which kill the target pest reported that *M. anisopliae* have larvicidal activity on mosquito larvae (Petlamul and Prsaertsan, 2012; Benserradj and Mihoubi, 2014). The use of *M. anisopliae* reduced the infestation of rice black bud significantly (Sumathi and Ramasubramanian, 2013). It was reported the larvicidal activities of *B. bassiana* against house fly *Musca domestica* L. (Diptera: Muscidae) (Mishra *et al.* 2010) which is of the same family as African Rice Gall Midge. The EPF used to treat crop pests have been shown to cause reduction on the plant physiology, agronomy and yield (Oyetunji *et al.* 2012; Oyetunji *et al.* 2024). It is therefore imperative to evaluate the entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) on rice plants because it provides the biological, environmentally safe and eco-friendly approach to managing AfRGM at the egg stage which is the penultimate stage to the destructive stage (larvae stage) of infestation without side effect on the plant or the environment unlike the synthetic insecticides. This study paves way to advancing the new approach of managing AfRGM holistically and make possible development on the mass production and assessment of EPF to managing other rice gall midges in other countries and continents of the world. The current study aimed at assessing the efficacy of *Metarhizium anisopliae* strains at managing AfRGM eggs in rice-based cropping systems without negative impact on the rice crop's physiology and agronomy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Paddy soil was collected from AfricaRice lowland rice field and sterilised at the Nematology Laboratory of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan. The sterile soil was filled into pots when sufficiently cool. Rice variety used for the study was ITA 306 which was susceptible to infestation of AfRGM. The experiment was conducted in a greenhouse under average temperature of 28.5 °C from April-September, 2016.

Seeds were sown at the rate of one seedling per hill in the seed boxes. Seedlings were transplanted to the pots containing sterile paddy soil 21 days after seeding. Four seedlings were transplanted in a pot on a spacing of 20 cm between hills with one seedling per hill. The pot containing seedling was placed in the wooden screening cages (cage size: 1x1x1.5 m) covered with screen. A basal dose of NPK at the rate 40:40:40 kg ha⁻¹ was applied at transplanting while top-dressing of urea 40 kg ha⁻¹ was applied at 20 days after transplanting (DAT).

Five adults AfRGM (2-males and 3-females) were introduced into each cage containing the rice seedlings for the purpose of mating for oviposition. The eggs were laid on the leaf of rice plant 24 h later and

were counted with the aid of hand lens and recorded. The experiment was laid out using Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications. In accordance with the Benserradj and Mihoubi¹¹, a total of 0.05 g of spore- inoculum of each fungal strain was prepared with 9 mL of sterile distilled water with average spore concentration of 1x10⁸. The treatments were applied separately on the leaf of rice plant containing the AfRGM eggs four days after transplanting, using hand-held sprayer. The eleven treatments include the three strains of *Beauveria bassiana* [Bba 326 (BA), Bba 5653 (BB) and Bba 5654 (BC)], three strains of *Metarhizium anisopliae* [Meta31 (MA), IC30 (MB) and IC20 (MC)] as well as the female only control (CF), male only control (CM), synthetic insecticide (CCF), water control (CW) and uninfested control (UIF). The selected fungi strains were the highly constructive strains from the pre-screening and evaluation conducted before this experiment. Females AfRGM only and AfRGM male only were added as a check to ensure certainty and add credibility to the authenticity of the sex ratio in all the treatments.

The data collection anchored on the life cycle of the pest and the developmental stage of the rice plant for pest infestation. Data were collected from 4 hills in a pot and 3 pots in a cage. The tiller infestation was the number of infested tillers (tiller with gall shoot) over total number of tiller per hill per cage in percentage. The average data per pot and cage was calculated and recorded. To determine the effect of the infestation and fungal treatment on the developmental stage of the rice plant, the following data were collected; panicle number, plant height, leaf length, leaf breadth, Panicle number, panicle length, grain number and grain weight. Data were collected weekly beginning from 21 days after treatment in consideration to the life cycle of the pest at the vegetative developmental stage of the crop. Non-infested tillers were taken and the percentage of the average Non-infestation Tiller Advantage Over the Control (NITAOC) was calculated per treatment as the absolute difference between treatment variables and the control divided by the control in percentage using this formular:

$$\% \text{ NITAOC} = \frac{(\text{Treatment} - \text{Control})}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

The data was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and General Linear Model (GLM) and the analysis was set to determine the level of correlation between the infestation and the plants' physiological and agronomical parameters with the correlation matrix using the SAS 9.2 Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) to separate means at a significance level of p<0.05.

RESULTS

The study showed the effect of the three strains of *M. anisopliae* and the three strains of *B. bassiana*. It showed that *M. anisopliae* strains controlled AfRGM eggs to a greater degree than *B. Bassiana* strains. The rice plant treated with MA had the least percentage tiller infestation ($13.33\pm 0.4\%$) on the rice plant and the greatest control over AfRGM eggs among the three strains of *M. anisopliae* and the 6 EPF overall. While only BC of *B. bassiana* had significant effect to controlling AfRGM at 70 DAT with 18.52% tiller infestation, all the *M. anisopliae* fungal strains (MA, MB, MC) had significant control effect over AfRGM with 13.33 ± 0.4 , 21.02 ± 0.4 and $13.38\pm 0.5\%$ tiller infestation at 70 DAT respectively (Table 1). Among the six EPF strains used, MC had the highest percentage of mean tiller infestation of $27.80\pm 0.5\%$ at the end of the experiment followed by BB with $26.3\pm 0.3\%$ mean tiller infestation (Table 1).

The study revealed that the chlorophyll content during the vegetative stage of rice in each the treatment was high and gradually decreased as the plants approached maturity. Plants that were not infested with AfRGM eggs had the highest chlorophyll content while those infested with AfRGM egg without treatment had significantly lower chlorophyll content (Table 1). The plant treated with AfRGM eggs and fungi had in consequential lower chlorophyll content than the plants treated with only AfRGM eggs (Table 1). There was no significant reduction in the chlorophyll content of rice plants treated with EPF only. At the end of the experiment, CM infested rice plants had the highest mean chlorophyll content followed by CF infested rice plants and rice plants treated CCF. The effect of AfRGM and the EPF on the stem girth of the rice plant was equally shown. The rice plants treated with CM had significantly highest stem girth followed by the uninfested rice plants and rice plants treated with CCF. Among the plants treated with EPF, *B. bassiana* Bba5653 had relatively high mean stem girth of 0.48 ± 0.05 cm followed by *M. anisopliae* IC30 with mean stem girth of 0.39 ± 0.03 cm (Table 1). Generally, aside the controls (UIF and CCF), MA had the highest percentage of uninfested tillers among the EPFs (84.13%) followed by MB, BC, BA with 78.21 , 76.78 and 76.52% of uninfested tillers respectively (Fig. 1). Rice plants treated with MA had the highest NITAO with 22.19% followed by MB with 13.60% NITAO (Fig. 2).

The study showed the effect of AfRGM infestation and the EPF on the plant height, leaf length and leaf breadth of different treatments (Table 2). While there was a reduction on the plant height of the plant treated with AfRGM, there was no negative effect of EPF on the plant height compared to the uninfested control. Plants treated with BB had the highest plant height of 97.50 cm followed by the plant treated with MB with the plant height of 97.17 cm. No data at maturity was collected from rice plants treated with CF and CW as all the hills and tillers were destroyed by the gall midge. In the same vein, there were no leaves on the rice plant treated with CF and CW for the leaf length and leaf breadth data collection. The rice plants treated with CM had the longest flag leaf at 41.00 ± 0.6 cm followed by the rice plants treated with CCF and UIF with 40.57 and 39.93 cm respectively (Table 2). The leaf breadth followed the same trend. The plant with the longest leaf had the widest breadth. Although there was significant reduction in the plant height of plants treated with some EPFs, there was no apparent difference in the flag leaf breadth of the EPF treated plants and the controls (Table 2).

The level of the relationship of all morphological characters was identified by phenotypic correlation coefficient (Table 3). The correlation coefficient showed the negative effect of infestation on the plant agronomy and physiology without EPFs negative impact on the morphological characteristics. The tiller infestation at 49DAT had positive correlation with the mean tiller infestation and tiller infestation at 70DAT. Mean tiller infestation was negative correlated with chlorophyll content at 70DAT, girth at 49DAT and girth at 70DAT. The tiller infestation at 49DAT had negative correlation with plant height, leaf length, leaf breadth, panicle length and grain weight. EPF treatments had no significant effect on the crop physiology and yield.

DISCUSSION

Assessment of the pest infestation on the rate of the effectiveness of the treatments applied showed increase in the level of infestation as the plant continued to grow in this study. This upsurge in the level of infestation was as a due to the build-up of the insect population which resulted to different generations. Although, the level of infestation of the EPF dwindled when compared with the control, yet there were variations in the level of the reduction based on the trait of each treatment. The *M. anisopliae* Meta31 treatment had low pest infestation in the amount of gall formed in the tillers infested with eggs. This result is in conformity with the findings of Rodrigues *et al.* (2014), who observed that the eggs of (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) were highly

Table1: Percentage of infested tiller, chlorophyll and girth after treatment with Entomopathogenic fungi on AfRGM eggs infested rice

Treat-ments	Tiller infestation (%)			Chlorophyll content (nmols cm ⁻²)			Stem girth (cm)		
	49 DAT	70 DAT	Mean	49 DAT	70 DAT	Mean	49 DAT	70 DAT	Mean
BA	12.05	34.87	23.42	23.46	18.39	23.24	0.30	0.33	0.29
BB	20.19	29.64	26.30	29.76	21.85	27.11	0.54	0.57	0.48
BC	24.28	18.52	24.38	23.36	20.38	24.01	0.52	0.33	0.27
MA	19.17	13.33	16.41	19.60	18.95	20.05	0.31	0.36	0.24
MB	18.27	21.02	23.84	30.36	22.43	26.87	0.39	0.33	0.39
MC	25.40	13.38	27.80	26.19	20.28	24.28	0.18	0.22	0.18
CCF	13.84	15.98	11.68	33.10	31.88	31.45	0.55	0.53	0.51
CF	38.11	17.82	31.70	30.16	26.17	26.75	0.37	0.44	0.31
CM	00.00	00.00	00.00	33.12	36.70	33.97	0.77	0.85	0.81
CW	29.41	45.61	34.62	28.38	32.94	30.98	0.59	0.49	0.43
UIF	00.00	00.00	00.00	33.14	35.85	32.05	0.71	0.65	0.67
MEAN	18.25	19.12	20.01	28.24	25.98	27.34	0.47	0.46	0.41
LSD	30.87	39.21	30.38	10.72	18.63	12.59	0.39	0.33	0.31
CV	60.37	68.31	66.89	15.38	25.85	17.70	36.1	36.73	44.37

BA: Bba326, BB:Bba5653, BC:Bba5654, MA: Meta31, MB: IC30, MC: IC20, CW: Water treatment, CF: Female treatment only, CM: Male treatment only, CCF: Synthetic insecticide, UIF: Uninfested control, TI: Tiller Infestation and DAT: Days after transplanting

Fig. 1: Mean percentage of non-infested tillers of rice plants infested with AfRGM eggs after treated with entomopathogenic fungi

BA: Bba326, BB:Bba5653, BC:Bba5654, MA: Meta31, MB: IC30, MC: IC20, CW: Water treatment, CF: Female treatment only, CM: Male treatment only, CCF: Synthetic insecticide, UIF: Uninfested control, TI: Tiller Infestation and DAT: Days after transplanting

Fig. 2: Percentage of non-infested tiller advantage over control of entomopathogenic fungi on rice plants infested with AfRGM eggs

BA: Bba326, BB:Bba5653, BC:Bba5654, MA: Meta31, MB: IC30, MC: IC20, CW: Water treatment, CF: Female treatment only, CM: Male treatment only, CCF: Synthetic insecticide, UIF: Uninfested control, TI: Tiller Infestation and DAT: Days after transplanting. No data obtained at CW

Table 2: Agronomic parameters of rice plants infested with AfRGM eggs after treatment with entomopathogenic fungi

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf breadth (cm)
BA	86.87	27.43	1.73
BB	97.50	34.83	1.33
BC	48.60	19.47	1.60
MA	68.80	26.60	1.40
MB	97.17	29.17	1.73
MC	79.23	17.70	1.20
CCF	81.60	40.57	1.57
CF	0.00	0.00	0.00
CM	77.97	41.00	1.87
CW	0.00	0.00	0.00
UIF	87.57	39.93	1.87
MEAN	66.21	25.16	1.48
Lsd	16.94	12.33	0.73
Cv	51.21	55.93	62.44

BA: Bba326, BB: Bba5653, BC: Bba5654, MA: Meta31, MB: IC30, MC: IC20, CW: Water treatment, CF: Female treatment only, CM: Male treatment only, CCF: Synthetic insecticide, UIF: Uninfested control, TI: Tiller Infestation and DAT: Days after transplanting.

Table 3: Relationship between tiller infestation and plant agronomy of rice infested with AfRGM eggs and treated with Entomopathogenic fungi

	TI49DAT	TI70DAT	TIMEAN	CHL49DAT	CHL70DAT	MEANCHL	GRT49DAT	GRT70DAT	GRTMEAN	PLTHGT	LEFLENT	LEFBRET	PANLENT	GRAINWT
TI49DAT	1													
TI70DAT	0.46**	1												
TIMEAN	0.89***	0.69***	1											
CHL49DAT	-0.12	0.13	-0.17	1										
CHL70DAT	-0.35	-0.01	-0.45*	0.64***	1									
MEANCHL	0.04	-0.08	-0.03	0.42*	0.18	1								
GRT49DAT	-0.43*	-0.02	-0.46*	0.68***	0.69***	0.09	1							
GRT70DAT	-0.39	-0.18	-0.50**	0.65***	0.81***	0.24	0.76***	1						
GRTMEAN	0.08	-0.01	0.02	0.28	0.28	0.05	0.27	0.25	1					
PLTHGT	-0.06	0.14	0.03	0.14	-0.08	-0.29	0.03	0.04	0.14	1				
LFBRET	-0.25	-0.14	-0.28	0.11	0.04	-0.23	0.16	0.23	0.10	0.80***	1			
PANLENT	-0.03	-0.12	-0.08	-0.21	-0.14	-0.32	0.01	-0.09	0.01	0.47	0.52	1		
GRAINWT	-0.05	0.12	0.02	0.08	-0.16	-0.30	-0.02	-0.06	0.06	0.83***	0.77***	0.50**	1	
	-0.15	-0.01	-0.081	-0.07	-0.12	-0.36	0.05	0.04	0.07	0.87***	0.79***	0.74***	0.76***	1

TI49DAT: Tiller infestation at 49 days after treatment, TI70DAT: Tiller infestation at 70 days after treatment, TIMEAN: mean tiller infestation, CHL49DAT: Chlorophyll at 49 days after treatment, MEANCHL: Mean chlorophyll,

CHL70DAT: Chlorophyll at 70 days after treatment, GRT49DAT: Girth at 49 days after treatment, PLTHGT: Plant height, PANLENT: Panicle length,

LEFLENT: Leaf Length, LFBRET: Leaf breadth, 100-GRAINWT: Grain weight. *, **, ***: significant at P = 0.05, 0.01, 0.001; values without a star are not significant

susceptible to *M. anisopliae* infection. The pathogenic characteristics of *M. anisopliae* on ticks' eggs discovered by Gindin (Gindin *et al.* 2009). The reason for the pathogenic characteristics of *M. anisopliae* is not far-fetched from the finding of Cloyd *et al.* (1999) who stated that *M. anisopliae* caused a systemic infection in the insect and deplete nutrients. *Metarhizium* spp are soil-dwelling fungi that live all over the world (Ugine, 2000). The virulence of *M. anisopliae* to eggs and immature stages of *Stomoxys calcitrans* L. (Diptera: Muscidae) by Moraes (Moraes *et al.* 2008). The *M. anisopliae* Meta31 could be found among the valuable biological control agents, due to their wide host range that often results in natural epizootics. However, the study showed that *B. bassiana* strain-Bba5653 with highest percentage mean infestation followed by *M. anisopliae* IC20 and other strains could not be used for control of AfRGM eggs as they had no effect on eggs. This finding was in accordance with the findings of Bricca *et al.* (2014) who stated that two commercial *Beauveria* strains were not pathogenic to third-instar larvae of Mango blossom gall midge *Procontarinia mangiferae* (Felt) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae). Also *Metarhizium brunneum* had low pathogenic effect on the pest in the interaction of predatory midge Aphidoletes, *M. Brunneum* and *Diabrotica virgifera* (Azevedo *et al.* 2017). These results showed that not all EPF will work the same way. Thus, establishing the specificity of entomopathogenic fungi to different insect pests

Moreover, there was no significant reduction in the chlorophyll content of the plant treated with EPF. Thus, the EPF has no side effect on the physiology of the rice plant. Even though no work has been reported on the effect of EPF on chlorophyll content of rice plant, the study of Chrispaul *et al.* (2010) revealed that the early stages of leaf growth, synthesis of chlorophyll, proteins and structural compounds were high resulting in high catabolic rates to support energy needs by the plants. Meanwhile, according to the study conducted by Oyetunji *et al.* (2012) stated that both *Botryodiplodia theobromae* and *Trichoderma sp.* inoculation in some rice genotypes caused reduction in chlorophyll content and emphasised that the fungi caused rot in the plants and equally worked in synergy with the termites on rice plant, thereby causing more deterioration. The EPF had no negative effect on the plant morphology as there was no significant effect on the stem girth and plant height.

The plants in the control without AfRGM (uninfested control) had high chlorophyll content while those treated with adult AfRGM had significantly lower chlorophyll content. It therefore means that each entomopathogenic fungi did not affect the chlorophyll content of the plants. The chlorophyll content at the beginning was high at vegetative stage. The high chlorophyll content is in accordance with the findings of other authors, who reported that during early stages of leaf growth, synthesis of chlorophyll, proteins and structural compounds were high resulting in high catabolic rates to support energy needs by the plants (Chrispaul *et al.* 2010; Oyetunji *et al.* 2012). As a result, it could be that those organisms were causative organisms of rot while the EPF used in this case were not traced to be pathogenic to the plant in any form but to the insect pest. Thus, it may be the reason for no reduction in the chlorophyll content in the current study. Consequently, photosynthesis was in full course and so there was no reduction. Neither the enzymes nor the biochemical reactions were affected or denature in any way by the EPF. Reduction in the chlorophyll content in some treatment was as a result of pest infestation. The phenotypic correlation coefficient showed the relationship between the plants' morphological characters affected by treatments. The negative correlation of the mean tiller infestation with the chlorophyll content, plant leaf and other traits is a response to the effect of the infestation of hatched eggs had on the plants. Such infestation affected the yields which entomopathogenic fungi can reduced and thus improve food security *M. anisopliae*-Meta31 can be used to controlling oviposition of AfRGM on rice without any adverse effect on the plant agronomy, physiology or yield. Apart from the EPF effect on controlling the AfRGM, effect of the EPF can be evaluated on the plants' growth parameter and associated basic nutrient infusion that aid the plant growth. This study has revealed the efficacy of entomopathogenic fungi especially *M. anisopliae*-Meta31 for controlling AfRGM infestation on rice plant.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the effectiveness of *M. anisopliae*-Meta31 to control the AfRGM eggs without any associated negative effect of the EPF on the plant physiology, agronomy or yield parameter. The study has discovered the efficacy of *M. anisopliae*-Meta31 that can be used to control AfRGM in rice base cropping system. The study will help researchers to uncover critical areas of using EPF for pest management and plant fertility instead of using mineral nutrient which many researchers were not able to explore.

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